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Towards a Business Matchmaking Tool for Entrepreneurial Engineering Students and Entrepreneurs

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INTRODUCTION

Educational context

The Faculty of Engineering Technology of KU Leuven participates in the Postgraduate Programme in Innovation and Entrepreneurship in Engineering [5]. This postgraduate programme is a joint initiative of faculties of the five Flemish universities that offer programmes in industrial sciences, biosciences, bioengineering and engineering sciences with the support of the Flemish Agency for Innovation and Entrepreneurship (VLAIO). The postgraduate programme aims to ensure that students are better prepared for the practice of their profession by focusing on the development of innovation competences, and enterprising and professional skills aside from technical engineering skills. The need for such a programme for engineers together with several educational methods to develop engineers in entrepreneurship in the context of an educational programme, are already discussed

in more detail in [1, 2, 4]. The postgraduate programme offers students three types of personal training projects: a team project, an in-company project or a start-up project. Discussing all three training projects is out of the scope of this work, but more information can be found in [5]. However, the start-up project is clearly the most important type of training project for the business matchmaking tool introduced in this paper. During the start-up training project, students get the chance to investigate the feasibility of a business idea, to implement a functional prototype as a proof-of-concept of the business idea, and to build up a business network. All of this is done within a safe educational environment under the supervision of business coaches, inspired by the ideas of a lean start-up [9]. Business coaches can advise students on technology and business aspects as they have a technological background as well as expertise in entrepreneurship. The quality of the start-up project is not measured in terms of ending up with a private start-up company, but it's of course not discouraged to do so.

Problem statement

Based on our experience in running the start-up project in the postgraduate programme for several years now, we notice that many of these students do not leave the postgraduate programme with an entrepreneurial adventure waiting to enter. There are various problems identified that can explain this, which will be addressed in more detail below. Another observation that can be made is that some students don't enter the postgraduate programme because of the perception that the focus is only on a private start-up. Some students are entrepreneurial students but don't want to become a full entrepreneur. Actually, a joint start-up with an entrepreneur, starting a new business from the ground up within an existing company or, in general, an entrepreneurial project, are equally well start-up training projects that the postgraduate programme is targeting. This finding is also confirmed by [6].

In the remaining part of this section, we discuss several problems mainly related to the first observation described above. A first problem is related to the initial business idea. At the start of the postgraduate programme, start-up students make a more extensive evaluation of their initial business idea by finding answers to three key questions. The first question forces the students to investigate the technological feasibility of their business idea. This question should be the easiest to answer as all students have an engineering background. Nevertheless, the answer to this question regularly reveals several major problems such as very high R&D efforts to build the product, intellectual property issues or high investment costs. The second question probes if the business idea meets the market, e.g. does it solve a so called 'customer-pain'. Forcing the students to meet with a potential customer often results in an interesting reality check that clearly illustrates that ideas should start from a customer's viewpoint and not from an engineer's perspective. Finally, the third question assesses the economic feasibility of the business idea. The latter question is the hardest to answer for our students as they typically lack valuable economical background expertise. After the answers on these questions are collected and analyzed, many students conclude that their initial business idea needs serious modifications or is not viable at all. Many students get stuck in fixing this issue. In conclusion, the first problem is about the availability of realistic business ideas for engineers as an inspiration source for their own ideas or as the starting point of an entrepreneurial project.

A second problem is related to a minimal set of team roles needed to run a start-up. Successful engineering start-ups need at least a technological expert, salesman and manager. These roles are seldom available in a single person which makes that some students decide they better not enter the training project. A well-chosen

cooperating entrepreneurial team can solve this issue. Unfortunately, the choice of the entrepreneurial team is currently rather limited in the educational environment of the postgraduate programme. Moreover, a few years of experience for some of these team roles can greatly increase the chances of success of the start-up. Hence, the second problem is about the availability of entrepreneurial minded people – having some experience is an extra benefit – willing to collaborate in an entrepreneurial relationship with students.

1 BUSINESS MATCHMAKING FOR ENTREPRENEURIAL STUDENTS

1.1 Business matchmaking approach

To tackle the observations and problems explained in the introduction, business coaches in the postgraduate programme experimented the last two academic years with a business matchmaking approach between entrepreneurial students and real-life entrepreneurs.

A cooperation with VOKA (Flanders' Chamber of Commerce and Industry) revealed that dynamic entrepreneurs often have valuable business ideas on the shelf but not always the time, the technological expertise, manpower or other resources available to translate these ideas in new business activities. Moreover, open-minded entrepreneurs are often willing to cooperate with students in the context of a joint-start-up or an entrepreneurial project within their company. Business ideas from entrepreneurs typically have some important advantages. Firstly, these business ideas are often demand-driven, i.e. based on requests from customers. That's already an excellent starting point to answer the second question of the business idea evaluation exercise. Secondly, an entrepreneur already critically looked at the economic feasibility of the business idea. Although this analysis is often more gut feeling than a deep economic analysis, it surely increases a positive outcome on the third question of the business idea evaluation exercise.

On the other hand, entrepreneurial students are young, flexible, highly motivated, social media skilled and well educated in engineering, but lack an inspiring business case or the experience of a real entrepreneur. These students can help in solving the resource problem of the entrepreneur. Especially their social media experience and knowledge on recent technologies (ICT, Internet-of-Things, Industry 4.0, AI, ...) can be very attractive in the digital transformation process of an existing company. Collaborating together with an entrepreneur creates by default an entrepreneurial team having several essential team roles on board to increase the viability of the entrepreneurial project. Moreover, the new team can profit from the existing business network of the entrepreneur. The entrepreneur can also choose to make financial or infrastructural resources available which again can boost the project. This solves at least partly the second problem described in the introduction.

1.2 Example cases

As mentioned above, the business matchmaking approach is already applied a few times in the past. We briefly discuss here two example cases.

In 2015, a student realized halfway the postgraduate programme that he was an entrepreneurial student for sure but less an entrepreneur. The technical and management skills were available, but taking risks inherently connected to entrepreneurship was not always acceptable to this student. Fortunately, he soon met a young entrepreneur in his business network who was looking for technological expertise to build a new innovative product to commercialize. He accepted the challenge to build this product as a freelancer. This was the start of a long term

cooperation between both. The product became successful and after his postgraduate program, he joined the entrepreneur's start-up as a shareholder and became the technology manager of the start-up. They worked on an improved version of the product and even started the launch of a second product in the same market. This example illustrates that entrepreneurial students should not always target a new start-up, but can become an important entrepreneurial member of an existing start-up.

A second example case was born out of a collaboration of KU Leuven and a local small and medium-sized enterprise (SME). In 2015, KU Leuven studied a proof-of-concept solution for a local SME to automate time registration and tracking of employees on building construction sites using a low-cost smartphone [8]. But many similar SME should have the same problem such that the idea of looking for a business case for this type of service became worth investigating. The owner and manager of the SME agreed on collaborating with entrepreneurial students to investigate the feasibility of the idea as a business product and, if successful, continue the collaboration as a start-up. The idea was proposed to students interested in the postgraduate programme and was picked up by a team of two electronics/ICT students. During the entire duration of the postgraduate programme, there was an intense collaboration between the SME owner, the students and a business coach with meetings every few weeks. A lot of effort was spent in developing a commercial prototype as this became a necessity to convince potential customers. Moreover, forced by legal regulations, a solution had to be developed to secure the privacy of the employees. At the end of the postgraduate programme in August 2017, one of the two students and the SME owner decided to continue their collaboration in a start-up.

2 BUSINESS MATCHMAKING TOOL

The main problem of the business matchmaking approach introduced in section 1 is the ad-hoc nature of this approach. Discovering business ideas from entrepreneurs strongly depends on the business network and the attention for this approach of the business coaches. Many companies are not aware of this initiative and consequently many business ideas are not revealed to the business coaches. There is no structural historical collection of business ideas and even exchanging business ideas between business coaches is not always sufficiently done. A similar situation as for entrepreneurs is true for engineering students. Many of them are not aware of the business ideas from, and the cooperation possibilities with an entrepreneur. Hence, they might miss the chance to start working on a strong business idea or even to participate to the postgraduate programme at all. It's also clear that the ad-hoc business matchmaking approach faces its limits when scaling up to larger numbers of business coaches, entrepreneurs and students. All these observations eventually led to the idea to design a web-based business matchmaking tool as a solution to the above mentioned problems. Moreover, this tool can also be used by students with a start-up looking for additional partners. The next subsection describes the functionality of the business matchmaking tool we have in mind while the final subsection briefly summarizes the technical design of the tool.

2.1 Requirements of the business matchmaking tool

The matchmaking tool should allow users - students and entrepreneurs - to create a profile, to upload business ideas and to send messages to take the first steps towards a potential collaboration. Currently, a LinkedIn login is required to use the matchmaking tool. Using the matchmaking tool without an account limits access to the landing pages. These landing pages are publicly accessible and provide the user

with enough explanation to what the goal of the tool is and who its primary target is. It also has a showcase of past projects with successful results. A user profile consists of a short bio and a list of skills, selectable from a list of tags, to assist a search tool. A business project page has a title, a project type, a short abstract, a more detailed project description and a set of project tags to ease searching. Settings allow to publish the project page anonymously or to hide confidential project information. A selected set of users can be given permission to read the hidden project details later on. The homepage of the tool allows users to search, to filter and to scroll through business projects. Business projects can be marked as favorite by adding them to a favorite list for quick access. Once a business project is selected, the public project details are shown as configured by the owner and a message can be sent to the owner to obtain more information or to discuss a cooperation. The first round of communication happens right in the tool itself using a basic chat-like messaging system. Messages are visualized in a message log for each business project separately. The matchmaking tool is designed with the focus on ease of use and not being too distracting. Big titles, short project descriptions and a system of tags and filters guide the user into selecting the projects in which he or she has an interest or finding another user with the skill-set required to make your own project a success. This makes sure the tool can be used across a vast number of professional sectors.

2.2 Design and development process

The matchmaking tool is created based on the principles that it must be easy, cheap and easy to adapt to how users actually use the matchmaking tool in order to improve the matchmaking experience and success. Therefore, an iterative development process with short loops of user feedback is used. This resulted in the choice of Django [7] as the web framework to build the tool. The main goal of Django is the rapid creation of complex, database-driven websites. Django allows for a lean development process with reiterations based on the short feedback loop. This helps in making sure the right tool is being build and the effort wasted on less required features is reduced to a minimum.

The matchmaking tool is mainly build upon a database, from which all the visual pages are constructed using templates. The database consists of projects, users, tags and message data and is built in a way that it is easy to extend or modify. The database tables and fields are specified as Python classes. Django will create the queries to perform all Create-Read-Update-Delete (CRUD) operations on the database. This means the database definition stays the same no matter what implementation is used. All queries are written as Python functions and translated by Django to the underlying database implementation (sqlite3 for example). By providing a database and templates, Django acts as a Model-View-Controller (MVC) that dynamically builds the web pages. These templates are generic Hypertext Markup Language (HTML) files with a Django-specific mini-language consisting of template-tags which allow for database access, if-cases, for-loops, parsing of strings, etc. This results in a loose coupling between the user interface and the database-driven back-end of the tool. Designing the templates thus is completely separated from the database and other back-end logic and can be done the same way other web pages are designed. The job of the MVC-controller is to make sure all the correct data is handed to the template files. Generated template files can be cached using Django's caching system for faster rendering times of the tool. Django's back-end also provides a number of features to ease developing such as authentication, authorization, sessions and an admin tool.

3 BUSINESS MATCHMAKING PROCESS

The business matchmaking tool introduced in section 2 only has meaning when integrated in a more comprehensive business matchmaking process. The current process contributes to five activities.

1. Collecting business ideas. This includes business cases that are free to use or require an entrepreneurial relationship with the owner.
2. Attracting open-minded entrepreneurs willing to establish an entrepreneurial relationship with students.
3. Attracting students with an entrepreneurial mindset looking for inspiration or a business cooperation.
4. Detecting a business matchmaking in making and facilitate the business matchmaking between the stakeholders.
5. Monitoring the tool to detect and to filter inappropriate usage, e.g. fake profiles, unrealistic business cases or abuse of the message functionality.

For all these activities, a number of actions are planned which will be briefly discussed now. The first three activities require creating awareness of the business matchmaking potential to mainly entrepreneurs, organizations involved in entrepreneurship and entrepreneurial students looking for business ideas or business partners. The business and certainly the student network of the business coaches in the postgraduate programme is a starting point but additionally an intense collaboration is set up with VOKA to promote business matchmaking with students among their impressive business network of companies and entrepreneurs. As VOKA regularly organizes business events and publishes a monthly business magazine, there are plenty of opportunities to launch and to repeat calls and to demonstrate the business matchmaking tool several times a year. Moreover, a web page with different successful example cases will be added to the business matchmaking tool to inspire visitors and to increase the attractiveness of the tool. The fourth and fifth activity strongly depend on the human interaction of the existing business coaches of the postgraduate programme and VOKA. Ideally, every user profile added to the tool is screened on the correct intentions. That shouldn't create a huge problem for student profiles as they already study in an engineering program of KU Leuven and, hence, quite some information can be easily obtained. A short interview is planned with active users – students as well as entrepreneurs – to make sure there is no misunderstanding on participating to the business matchmaking program. Monitoring messages and the message activity should help to detect an early business matchmaking case. In that situation, additional help will be offered to the involved actors such as, for example, the expertise of a business coach or advice related to the cooperation contract.

4 DISCUSSION

Remark that the business matchmaking tool is currently under development. As such, this is work in progress. Nevertheless, a limited survey was conducted among entrepreneurs on a business event of VOKA to obtain feedback on the business matchmaking idea and to map their view on the business matchmaking tool [3]. A number of conclusions can be drawn from this survey (i) most entrepreneurs have one or more business ideas but lack resources to execute them, (ii) the idea of business matchmaking using a digital tool is welcomed positively and many of the business idea owners would like to stay involved when the idea is realized, (iii) entrepreneurs often attach importance to controlling who has access to the publication of their profiles and the business ideas, mainly because of competitors of

the company they run, (iv) the business matchmaking tool should be reliable, and (v) tool usage should be efficient and may not consume a lot of time while still creating a kind of sense of community using digital interaction. This feedback is reflected as much as possible in the design of the business matchmaking tool, for instance, several settings to publish parts of information anonymously are included and only a limited amount of information is required to create a profile or upload a business idea. Moreover, the tool is not designed nor promoted as a time-consuming social media tool.

The business matchmaking tool and process will trial-run from September 2017 to August 2018, but smaller user tests are of course organized before that date and adjustments are made, if necessary. During the trial-run, we target a modest amount (i.e. around 50) of business ideas and business profiles of students and entrepreneurs, and a limited amount (i.e. around 5) of effective business matchmakings such that the corresponding workload, mainly created by activity 4 and 5 of the business matchmaking process, is manageable by the existing business coaches. In the future, other actors involved in business networking and entrepreneurship will be included, which will increase the demands and workload but also the number of business coaches. Nevertheless, it could be interested to investigate if artificial intelligence techniques could further automate these activities, but this is out of the scope of the current project.

Based on the business matchmaking cases set-up in the past without using the business matchmaking tool, we discovered some points of attention. Building a relation of trust between the actors involved in the business matchmaking process, takes time. Before the cooperation starts it's very important to discuss, preferably resulting in a signed cooperation contract, the modalities of the cooperation, e.g. ownership and intellectual property of the results so far, financial aspect, etc., in case the cooperation is terminated at some point in time. Another point of attention is a certain unbalance in the cooperation between a young and unexperienced student versus an experienced and often successful entrepreneur. These points of attention will not be solved by a digital matchmaking tool, but are additional tasks for the business coach to monitor.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Bosman, L., Fernhaber, S. (2018), *Teaching the Entrepreneurial Mindset to Engineers*, Springer International Publishing, Cham, Switzerland.
- [2] Craps, S., Pinxten, M., Saunders, G., Leandro Cruz, M., Gaughan K., Langie, G. (2017), *Professional Roles and Employability of Future Engineers*, 45th SEFI Annual Conference: Education Excellence for Sustainability, 18-21 Sept. 2017, Azores, Portugal, art.nr. 499-507.

- [3] Demuyt, L. (2017), Innovatiecase (Bachelor project), Erasmus Hogeschool Brussel.

- [4] Grecu, V., Denes, C. (2017), Benefits of Entrepreneurship Education and Training for Engineering Students, MATEC Web of Conferences, 121. 12007. 10.1051/mateconf/201712112007.

- [5] Haenen, C., Evers, K., Skenazi, A., Dewulf, K., Nietvelt, M. (2017), Postgraduate Programme in Innovation and Entrepreneurship in Engineering, Retrieved from www.innovationentrepreneurship.be.

- [6] Maritz, A., De Waal, G., Shieh, C.-J. (2014), Educating Engineers: A Postgraduate Entrepreneurship and Innovation Perspective, International Journal of Engineering Education, Vol. 30, No 2, pp. 291-301.

- [7] Nigel, G., (2016), Mastering Django: Core, GNW Independent Publishing, Hamilton NSW, Australia.

- [8] Oeyen, D., Gerrits, W. (2015), Isoltrack (Master thesis), KU Leuven.

- [9] Ries, E. (2011), The Lean Startup: How Today's Entrepreneurs Use Continuous Innovation to Create Radically Successful Business, Crown Business, New York.